

Impact of ECG Characteristics on Deep Classifiers

Tuija Leinonen, Jiawei Yang, David Wong, Antti Airola, and Matti Kaisti

Abstract—Deep learning has shown great promise in automating electrocardiogram (ECG) analysis, yet its performance varies significantly across different clinical settings and data conditions. This study systematically investigates how deep learning classifiers interact with ECG-related characteristics, as influenced by key data factors including data size, data augmentation, data filtering, signal length, and label correlations. We benchmark two representative architectures, ResNet and Transformer, on four public real-world ECG datasets. Our findings reveal that model performance varies substantially based on data factor configurations, often exceeding the performance gap between different model architectures. Notably, ResNet frequently outperforms Transformer under challenging conditions, not due to superior complexity, but due to greater robustness to data quality issues. These results underscore a critical gap in current ECG AI research: the underappreciation of data-centric optimization. Addressing this gap by integrating model development with informed data strategies is essential for unlocking the full potential of deep learning in real-world ECG analysis.

Index Terms—Electrocardiogram characteristics Data size Data augmentation Data filtering Signal length Label correlations Deep learning Multilabel learning Residual neural network Transformer neural network

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into ECG analysis has driven substantial progress in tasks like paper ECG interpretation [1], heartbeat classification [2], arrhythmia detection [3], and cardiovascular disease (CVD) classification [4]. This progress is largely fueled by the rapid advancement of AI techniques and the increasing availability of large-scale annotated ECG datasets. In particular, deep neural networks (DNNs) have become a popular choice for ECG analysis due to their powerful capability to automatically extract and learn complex patterns from non-stationary and highly variable ECG signals.

Many end-to-end DNN-based ECG classifiers have emerged, offering a key advantage over traditional methods by eliminating the need for manual feature engineering. For

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Tuija Leinonen, Jiawei Yang, Antti Airola, and Matti Kaisti are with the Department of Computing, University of Turku, Finland.

David Wong is with the Leeds Institute of Health Sciences, University of Leeds, UK.

Corresponding author: Matti Kaisti (E-mail: mkaisti@utu.fi)

instance, Lu et al. [5] developed a DNN model to classify single-lead ECG signals into four categories, while Hannun et al. [6] proposed a DNN capable of classifying 12 types of arrhythmias. Extending to multi-lead ECGs, Chen et al. [7] introduced a multi-channel, multi-scale DNN model to classify 9-lead ECG recordings. Moving beyond whole ECG classification, Xu et al. [8] explored beat-by-beat classification using DNNs. Furthermore, to address the computational complexity of DNN models, Xiao et al. [9] designed a lightweight convolutional neural network (CNN) that achieves competitive performance with reduced resource requirements.

Despite these advancements, the potential synergistic interaction between DNN-based ECG classifiers and various data-related factors remains largely unexplored. This poses a crucial question for the research community: *How significantly do DNN-based ECG classifiers respond to the joint configuration of data-related factors?* Addressing this question is vital for optimizing the performance of all data-driven models, including DNNs.

To address this gap, we conducted an empirical investigation into the influence of five key data-related factors on the performance of DNNs for ECG analysis. These factors are closely tied to the design and development of AI models. Our study provides valuable experimental evidence and practical insights that can guide ECG AI model developers, whether leveraging existing solutions or building new models, in optimizing their approaches for improved performance.

Our contribution in this work includes: (1) A comprehensive review of five key ECG data-related factors in Section II; (2) A systematic investigation of these five important ECG data-related factors using two state-of-the-art DNN models on four real-world ECG datasets, considering two scenarios with and without distribution shift; (3) Practical recommendations for default settings regarding these five critical ECG data-related factors based on our experiments.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related work on ECG data-related factors. Section III details the datasets, classifiers, experimental configurations for each factor under investigation, and the evaluation metrics. Section IV presents the experimental findings, followed by in-depth discussion and analysis of limitations. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

In ECG analysis, numerous data-related factors may influence model performance, such as ECG signal amplitude variability, data label inconsistencies, signal acquisition

timing, heart rate variability, artifact detection, and outlier identification. Other key considerations include variations in ECG lead configurations, multi-modal data integration, device-specific differences, and the impact of long-term data drift. Despite these factors, research has predominantly focused on five critical aspects: data size, data augmentation, data filtering, signal length, and label correlations. These factors have garnered more attention due to their direct influence on model accuracy and generalizability. Larger datasets are often necessary to train robust models, while data augmentation techniques improve model generalization, particularly in the case of rare events. Effective filtering techniques ensure high-quality input signals, and the appropriate segmentation of signal length is essential for capturing meaningful temporal features. Additionally, label correlations play a key role in handling multi-label tasks, yet often remain underexplored in relation to their impact on deep learning models for ECG analysis.

Data Size: The size of the training set, particularly the number of ECG recordings, is a critical factor influencing the performance of both traditional machine learning (ML) methods and recent AI models. Traditional ML algorithms, such as support vector machines and decision trees, typically operated on relatively small datasets with carefully engineered features. In contrast, recent deep learning-based approaches generally require substantially larger ECG datasets to achieve robust and accurate performance. For example, the PTB-XL database, containing over 21,000 10-second ECG records, has demonstrated that increasing data size can lead to significant performance improvements [10]. However, small dataset scenarios often result in overfitting and reduced generalization, which has motivated the adoption of techniques such as transfer learning [11], medical image classification with limited data [12], healthcare predictive modeling with small samples [13], and semi-supervised learning strategies [14]. Despite these efforts, systematic studies specifically analyzing the effect of ECG dataset size on the performance of deep models remain relatively sparse.

Data Augmentation: Data augmentation has become a key technique for addressing data scarcity in both traditional ML and AI-based image classification; however, its application in ECG analysis remains relatively underexplored [15]. In the context of ECG analysis, data augmentation is expected to help overcome the limited availability of annotated data, especially for rare cardiac conditions, with emerging studies beginning to explore this potential [16], [17]. Traditional ML approaches mainly relied on simple synthetic data generation through signal modeling or noise injection, while recent AI-based methods have adopted more sophisticated augmentation techniques, including random cropping, scaling, time warping, and generative adversarial network (GAN)-based synthesis, to enhance data diversity. For instance, Karhinoja et al. proposed a framework for generating synthetic biosignals including ECG [18], while GANs have been effectively used to synthesize ECG signals, leading to improved performance in arrhythmia classification tasks [19]. In addition, studies have demonstrated that augmented ECG data, particularly through adversarial learning or signal transformation, can improve both

classification accuracy and model robustness against noise and artifacts [20]. Furthermore, augmentation techniques are increasingly integrated with self-supervised learning frameworks to better utilize unlabeled ECG data [20]. Nevertheless, systematic investigations into the specific impact of augmented ECG data on deep model performance remain limited and warrant further research.

Data Filtering: ECG signals are frequently contaminated by various types of noise, including baseline wander, powerline interference, and motion artifacts [21], [22]. It is generally believed that preprocessing of ECG data through appropriate filtering techniques is crucial to improve signal quality before inputting into ML or AI models. Traditional ML pipelines have strongly depended on classical signal filtering methods, such as bandpass filtering, baseline wander removal, notch filtering [23]–[25], and wavelet-based denoising techniques [26], [27] to suppress noise artifacts. In contrast, recent deep learning models often incorporate learnable filters within their initial network layers, reducing the need for extensive manual preprocessing. Nevertheless, several studies have shown that applying suitable filtering methods prior to deep learning can still enhance model performance, particularly when dealing with noisy, real-world ECG recordings [28]. Moreover, adaptive and data-driven filtering techniques have emerged, aiming to optimize preprocessing specifically for AI models [29]. While existing guidelines on filtering parameters, such as bandwidth and cutoff frequencies, are primarily based on traditional ML frameworks [30]–[32], their specific influence on deep learning model performance remains unclear. Therefore, systematic studies investigating the role of ECG filtering in the context of deep models are still limited and warrant further exploration.

Signal Length: The length of the ECG signal, typically defined by the number of sampled points, plays a critical role in shaping both model architecture and performance. Traditional ML approaches often relied on fixed-length signal segments or extracted features from specific intervals, such as RR-intervals, to handle variability in signal duration. In contrast, recent AI models, particularly CNNs and recurrent neural networks (RNNs), can directly process raw ECG signals, with longer input lengths providing richer temporal and morphological information at the cost of increased computational complexity [33], [34]. While short ECG segments have been shown to be sufficient for detecting specific conditions like atrial fibrillation, other tasks, such as multi-label disease classification, generally benefit from longer signals that capture multiple cardiac cycles [35]. Advances such as attention mechanisms and sequence modeling have further enabled deep learning models to better handle long ECG signals without sacrificing performance [36]. However, despite these developments, there is a noticeable lack of systematic studies explicitly investigating the impact of signal length on the performance of deep learning models in ECG analysis. This remains an open research area warranting further exploration.

Label Correlations: In multi-label ECG classification tasks, whether to treat labels independently or to model their dependencies is an important consideration that can significantly influence model design and performance. Treating labels independently, as commonly done in traditional ML approaches,

simplifies the modeling process and avoids the risk of error propagation between labels. However, this approach ignores the inherent correlations among cardiac conditions, such as the frequent co-occurrence of atrial fibrillation with heart failure or other arrhythmias, which could provide valuable information for prediction. In contrast, recent AI models have attempted to capture label dependencies through techniques such as structured prediction, label attention mechanisms, or graph neural networks [37], [38]. Modeling label correlations allows for exploiting medical knowledge embedded in co-occurrence patterns, potentially improving performance, especially in cases with sparse or ambiguous signals. Nonetheless, dependency modeling can also increase model complexity and may introduce errors if the estimated correlations are inaccurate or dataset-specific. While initial studies have shown the benefit of capturing label relationships in medical data, systematic investigations into how label correlation modeling affects deep learning performance specifically in ECG analysis remain limited. Given the multi-faceted nature of cardiac diseases and their interrelated manifestations on ECG signals, understanding the trade-offs and effectiveness of label dependency modeling in deep models is an essential direction for future research.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

We used the harmonized 12-lead ECG dataset from [39]. The data is collected from two sources, the George B. Moody PhysioNet/CinC challenge 2021 (CinC) [40]–[42] and the Shandong Provincial Hospital (SPH) [43]. Following [39], we grouped the CinC data as four distinct datasets based on their initial origin: the Chapman-Shaoxing and Ningbo (CSN) dataset [44], [45], the CPSC and CPSC-Extra dataset [41], [46], the Georgia 12-lead ECG (G12EC) dataset [47], the PTB and PTB-XL dataset [48], [49]. We excluded the St Petersburg INCART 12-lead Arrhythmia database [50] due to its significant differences and small size compared to the included five datasets.

To harmonize the datasets, label mapping was required as the CinC data uses SNOMED CT codes but the SPH data follows the AHA standard for labeling. We selected a set of 17 CVD labels for our study based on two criteria: i) the labels were part of the PhysioNet/CinC challenge 2021 evaluation, and ii) each label appeared in at least four distinct datasets and with a minimum of 50 occurrences in each. Finally, as the sinus rhythm label is the AHA statements of the SPH data, we used logistic regression to impute the label to the data. We categorized the 17 selected labels into rhythm-based (affect the timing and regularity of heartbeats) labels and morphology-based (affect the shape or structure of ECG waves) labels. Rhythm-based labels refer to abnormalities such as sinus bradycardia, atrial flutter and premature atrial contraction mostly characterized by irregularities in peak intervals where as morphology-based labels refer to abnormalities within the cardiac cycle, including e.g. T wave abnormality, bundle branch blocks, and axis deviations. The selected labels, their corresponding frequencies and the categorization

Fig. 1: Overview of the training set and the two test sets. 39.1 % (16,290 ECGs) of the training set is from the SPH dataset, 35.8 % (14,921) is from the PTB and PTB-XL dataset, 14.9 % (6,225) is from the G12EC dataset, and the remaining 10.2 % (4,279) is from the CPSC and CPSC-Extra dataset.

are introduced in Table I. More information regarding the characteristics and harmonization of the datasets can be found in [39].

In this study, we evaluated the model performance using two different test sets: 1) in one test set, ECGs were sampled from a dataset of the same hospital as the training set, simulating a scenario where there is no distribution shift between the training and test sets; 2) in the other dataset, ECGs were sampled from a dataset of a different hospital from the training set, simulating a scenario where there is a distribution shift between the training and test sets. For the first scenario, four datasets – the CPSC and CPSC-Extra dataset, the G12EC dataset, the PTB and PTB-XL dataset, and the SPH dataset – were split using a 7:3 ratio, with multilabel stratification [51] applied within each dataset to preserve label proportions. 70 % of this split was used as the training set, while the remaining 30 % was used as the pooled test set, simulating a case where data to train and test a model is collected within the same source, e.g., one hospital. In the second scenario, we simulated the situation where patients come from a different hospital compared to the training context. For this, the CSN dataset was used as the distribution-shift test set. The training set and the two test sets, the pooled test set and the CSN test set, are illustrated in Figure 1.

In total, the training set contained 41,715 ECGs pooled from the four datasets, including 4,279 ECGs from the CPSC and CPSC-Extra dataset, 6,225 ECGs from the G12EC dataset, 14,921 ECGs from the PTB and PTB-XL dataset, and 16,290 ECGs from the SPH dataset. The pooled test set contained the remaining 17,909 ECGs from these datasets, and the CSN test set included 43,814 ECGs. The label distributions per each of these sets are summarized in Supplementary Table 1.

B. Evaluation Metrics

In this study, model performance was evaluated using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) [52]. For single-label classification tasks, standard AUC was employed, while both Macro-averaged AUC (Macro-AUC) and Micro-averaged AUC (Micro-AUC) metrics were utilized

TABLE I: Dataset Information (Labels marked with an asterisk indicate rhythm-based diagnoses.)

Labels (CVD name)	SNOMEDCTCode	Training set	Pooled test set	CSN test set	Total
lightgray Sinus rhythm*	426783006	26,303	11,275	8,125	45,703
lightgray Sinus bradycardia	426177001	3,549	1,521	16,559	21,629
T wave abnormal	164934002	4,699	2,016	7,043	13,758
lightgray Sinus tachycardia*	427084000	2,181	935	7,255	10,371
lightgray Atrial flutter	164890007	289	124	8,060	8,473
Left axis deviation	39732003	4,357	1,867	1,545	7,,769
lightgray Atrial fibrillation*	164889003	2,903	1,245	1,780	5,928
lightgray Sinus arrhythmia*	427393009	1,953	838	2,550	5,341
T wave inversion	59931005	901	386	2,877	4,164
1st degree AV block	270492004	1,993	854	1,192	4,039
Right bundle branch block	59118001	2,177	933	649	3,759
lightgray Premature atrial contraction*	284470004	1,585	680	1,312	3,577
Incomplete right bundle branch block	713426002	2,009	861	246	3,116
Left anterior fascicular block	445118002	1,372	588	380	2,340
Low QRS voltages	251146004	614	264	1,043	1,921
Right axis deviation	47665007	412	176	853	1,441
Left bundle branch block	164909002	788	337	240	1,365

for comprehensive assessment of multilabel classification performance. Macro-AUC operates as a class-averaged metric that first computes performance separately for each class before averaging the results. This method assigns equal importance to each label (or class, i.e., diagnostic category), ensuring rare conditions receive equivalent consideration to common ones, regardless of class prevalence. In contrast, Micro-AUC serves as an instance-level evaluation metric that assesses model performance by aggregating all individual predictions across classes into a unified binary classification task. This approach assigns equal weight to each prediction instance, irrespective of its class membership, thereby emphasizing overall discriminative capability.

C. Classifiers

To investigate the impact of data-related factors, we employed two state-of-the-art deep learning models from the PhysioNet/CinC Challenge 2020 [42], [53]: a Residual Neural Network (ResNet) [54] and a Transformer-based model [55]. To further understand the performance gains of these deep models, we also compared them against two widely-used traditional ML methods: Logistic Regression and XGBoost [56].

Data preprocessing was harmonized for both neural networks, and their respective descriptions can be found in [39]. The default parameters were used for all models, except for the logistic regression, we adjusted the maximum number of iterations to 2000 to ensure convergence. The transformer model also incorporates handcrafted features, following [55], so we extracted 20 ECG features from the lead II (Supplementary Material, Table 2). These features were used for logistic regression and XGBoost as well. In addition to the ECG features, the age and sex features were included for all models, including ResNet.

The results of the above four classifiers are shown in the Figure 2. ResNet and Transformer achieved Macro-AUC of 0.966 and 0.937 on the pooled test set, and 0.941 and 0.912 for the CSN test set, respectively. For Micro-AUC, the results were 0.982 and 0.972 on the pooled test set, and 0.930 and 0.918

on the CSN test set. The logistic regression and XGBoost models showed lower performance compared to the networks, with 0.153 and 0.135 lower Macro-AUC and 0.057 and 0.044 lower Micro-AUC on the pooled test set, and 0.142 and 0.155 lower Macro-AUC and 0.080 and 0.082 lower Micro-AUC on the CSN test set. The results demonstrate that i) both deep models outperform traditional ML models, and ii) ResNet consistently outperforms all other models, resulting in higher Macro- and Micro-AUCs on both test sets, and iii) the drop in performance of logistic regression and XGBoost is larger for Macro-AUC. The traditional models have large performance difference between the rhythm-based and morphology-based labels (Supplementary Material, Figures 7 and 8): For example, XGBoost, the better-performing model from the two, achieves performance comparable to that of the networks on the rhythm-based labels, resulting in over 0.9 AUCs for these labels, except for atrial flutter with 0.82 AUC on the CSN test set. However, both models struggle similarly with the morphology-based labels, resulting in 0.8 AUCs or lower for all labels, except for left axis deviation and left anterior fascicular block, which show AUCs ranging between 0.82–0.89, and XGBoost for left bundle branch block with the AUC of 0.83.

Consequently, we choose ResNet as the reference model to study the impact of ECG data-related factors in all experiments. In order to balance the need to obtain relatively more general conclusions and the limited pages of this journal, the Transformer model is also tested as the second reference model, but the experimental results of Transformer are provided in the supplementary material.

D. Experimental setups

To ensure a consistency across the experimental setups, we applied the following preprocessing steps for each ECG recording. The ECGs were resampled to 250 Hz and adjusted to a fixed size of 4,096 samples, that is approximately 16 seconds. Signals longer than that were randomly cropped, and shorter than that were padded with zeros on both sides, with a random ratio of zeros on each side, until the length reached

Fig. 2: Comparison between deep models (ResNet and Transformer) and non-deep models (Logistic Regression and XGBoost).

the target size. The signal amplitudes were normalized to the range between 0 and 1. The age values were divided by 100. The sex values were one-hot-encoded into two categories, male and female. Any adjustments done to these default settings are described in the respective experiment subsections.

The experiments were run using Python version 3.10.4 with Torch version 1.13.1. The neural networks were run and evaluated on the Puhti supercomputer, provided by the CSC – IT Center for Science Ltd. The logistic regression model was implemented using the scikit-learn library [57] version 1.2.0 and the XGBoost model was implemented using the xgboost library version 2.1.0. The code is freely available on GitHub, with the link provided in the Code Availability section.

1) *Data Size Settings*: As larger training data is expected to improve model generalization, we evaluated how predictive performance changes with data availability. This effect was studied by sampling 1 %, 5 %, 10 %, 20 %, and 50% of the ECGs from the original training set. This corresponds to approximately 420 signals for 1 %, 2,077 signals for 5 %, 4,170 signals for 10 %, 8,358 signals for 20 %, and 20,882 signals for 50 %. The total number of signals per sample varied slightly due to the inherent behavior of multilabel stratification [51] that was used to maintain a similar label distribution to that of the original training set. For each sample size of 1 %, 5 %, 10 %, and 20 %, ten random splits were sampled from the training set, while two splits were used for 50 %.

2) *Data Augmentation Settings*: A limited number of studies have explored augmentation techniques for ECG deep classification in the past. In this work, we systematically investigate these techniques and develop a set of augmentations based on existing literature (e.g. [15], [58]), evaluating their effects on overall temporal and morphological variations. The augmentations were designed not to significantly alter morphological details related to disease such as scaling of time intervals within the cardiac cycle. Furthermore, we extend previous efforts by introducing a randomization scheme that ensures each augmentation is unique. The primary objective of data augmentation is to enhance model robustness and generalization by artificially expanding the dataset and exposing models to diverse data variations.

We applied ten different augmentation methods to transform a given ECG signal, including: i) horizontal or ii) vertical flipping, iii) amplitude scaling using a sine wave, iv) amplitude

scaling using a triangular pattern, v) scaling by a vector with linearly increasing or decreasing values, vi) adding random Gaussian noise, vii) applying a notch filter, viii) using a rolling operation to shift the signal along the time axis, ix) stretching or compressing the signal along the time axis by resampling to decrease or increase the signal’s duration, and x) modifying the sampling intervals using a scaling vector with linearly increasing or decreasing sample intervals.

A randomization scheme was used in each method. The effect of each augmentation is controlled by one or two input parameters. These parameters define the limits of a range from which a random scaling factor is drawn using a uniform distribution each time an augmentation is applied. This value determines the effect of the augmentation, while the defined parameters control the range and thus how much the each specific method can vary between different augmentation realizations. The parameters influencing these methods were selected based on visual inspection of their effects on randomly chosen ECG signals, ensuring that maximal deviation still resembled an ECG and retained visible R-peaks. The random scaling factors for the multiplication functions (iii–v), the time-scaling functions (xi–x), and the noise function were drawn from a uniform distribution. The transformations applied in the multiplication functions (iii–v) are randomly generated for each channel. For the roll function, the shift direction, right (value of 1) or left (value of -1), was first randomly selected, followed by the shift magnitude, which was determined by a random integer drawn from a uniform distribution.

The augmentation experiments in our study were divided into two sets, where we investigated i) each augmentation method individually with a fixed probability it being applied on the recording using full training data, and ii) all augmentations applied sequentially. The sequential application of methods was evaluated on different sizes of training data, including the full set as well as the smaller samples (Section III-D.1). The augmentation methods were applied to an ECG signal based on a probability value p_1 , which was independently defined for each method. Another probability, p_2 , determined whether any augmentation was applied to the signal at all. In the first experimental setup, the fixed probabilities were set as $p_1 = 0.5; p_2 = 1$, that is, a method had a 50 % chance of being applied, while the overall augmentation process was guaranteed to occur. For the second experimental setup for the augmentations, all the methods were used sequentially and each of them were considered to be applied with a probability p_1 . We evaluated multiple values of p_1 to different sizes of training data, that is, 1, 5, 10, 20 and 50 % samples as well as the full training set. The sequentially applied augmentation experiments followed the steps: i) we selected the values for p_1 from the set $\{0.1, 0.5\}$ and the values for p_2 from the set $\{0.2, 0.5, 0.8\}$, resulting in six sets of probabilities. ii) The probability sets were evaluated on three sample sizes (1, 5, and 10 %) from the training set size experiments as well as the full training set. We limited these experiments to three samples for each sample size in total and used only the ResNet model due to computational constraints. iii) Based on the results, the probability sets of $\{p_1 = 0.1; p_2 = 0.5\}$ and $\{p_1 = 0.5; p_2 = 0.1\}$ performed the best on average across all given training

data sizes. We selected these two sets for more comprehensive evaluation, testing them extensively across all training data samples to obtain the final results for the sequentially applied augmentations experiments.

3) Data Filtering Settings: As filtering impacts the preservation of diagnostically relevant features, we investigate different bandwidths to evaluate their effect on predictive performance and optimal feature representation. For this set of experiments, the ECGs were resampled to 500 Hz and adjusted to a fixed size of 8,192 samples to ensure the accurate capture of frequencies up to 150 Hz. The effect of bandwidth was investigated with and without applying filters. We used i) a bandpass filter with cutoff frequencies of 0.67 and 40 Hz which are typical and recommended for wearable ECG devices [59], ii) a low-pass filter with a cutoff frequency of 150 Hz, following the recommendations for clinical-grade bandwidth [32]. We also investigated the impact of significantly reducing the bandwidth by varying the upper cutoff frequency of a bandpass filter. Specifically, we adjusted the cutoff frequency to 1, 5, 10, and 20 Hz. The lower cutoff frequency was not modified, as the signals are only 10 seconds in length for most part, meaning there are no low-frequency components to filter out with lower cutoffs.

4) Signal Length Settings: Longer signals provide more temporal context and analyzing signal length provides insights into how much temporal information is necessary for accurate predictions, particularly when considering the morphological and rhythmic features of an ECG signal. While the morphological features rely more on information from one cardiac cycle, the rhythm patterns are more dependent on the intervals between the cycles. To investigate the effect of signal length, each ECG was shortened to 10 % and 50 % of the original length. The start index for the shortened signal was randomly selected so that the selected proportion for the new length was ensured to stay within the bounds of the original length. The majority of the ECG signals in the training set (34,947 signals or 83.78 %) had a length of 10 seconds. Additionally, 29 signals (0.07 %) ranged from 5 to 10 seconds, 5,767 signals (13.82 %) ranged from 10 to 20 seconds, and 896 signals (2.15 %) ranged from 20 to 60 seconds, while the remaining 76 signals (0.18 %) extended up to 120 seconds in length.

5) Label Correlations Settings: Given a multi-label classification task, where each label corresponds to a specific CVD, we explore the role of label correlations by training models on these labels either jointly or independently. Specifically, we first train a multi-label classifier using all 16 CVD labels to predict them simultaneously. Then, we train 17 separate binary classifiers, each dedicated to predicting a single CVD. Furthermore, to investigate the interaction between label correlation and data size, we conduct experiments using either the full training set or a subset of it as shown in Section III-D.1.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To comprehensively evaluate the impact of different factors, we performed consistency analyses from five key perspectives: (1st) Changes in Macro-AUC on the pooled dataset with ResNet when varying the settings for the studied factor,

(2nd) Comparison between Macro-AUC and Micro-AUC on the pooled dataset with ResNet, (3rd) Comparison between rhythm-based and morphology-based diseases on the pooled dataset with ResNet, (4th) Comparison between two test sets with ResNet, (5th) Comparison between ResNet and Transformer models. Our analysis revealed consistent patterns across these dimensions - in most cases, the results for each studied factor aligned with observations from previous perspectives regarding that factor. The following subsections detail the results for each factor studied under each perspective and the differences between different perspectives. *For consistency across figures, the test performance of ResNet is indicated by horizontal lines: the blue dotted line represents the pooled test set, while the orange dash-dotted line corresponds to the CSN test set. To save space, other experimental results including Transformer's can be found in the supplementary material.*

A. Data Size

Figure 3 summarizes the test results of training the reference model (ResNet) with different training set sizes. We can observe the following.

Changes in Macro-AUC on the pooled dataset with ResNet when varying the settings for data size: ResNet maintains stable Macro-AUC performance when trained on 50% of the original dataset (41,715 signals), with 0.02 AUC difference even at 20% training data (8,358 ECGs). Performance gradually declines when reducing data from 50% to 5% (0.04 AUC drop between steps), with the most severe degradation occurring between 5% and 1% training data (0.14 AUC decrease). This suggests ResNet requires at least 5% of the original data (2,077 signals) to maintain reasonable performance.

Comparison between Macro-AUC and Micro-AUC on the pooled dataset with ResNet: As the size of the training set decreases, the behavior of the Micro-AUC is similar to the Macro-AUC, as introduced above, but the gap between the Micro-AUC and the Macro-AUC becomes smaller. This may be due to the smaller differences between labels (i.e., diseases) when the training set is smaller.

Comparison between rhythm-based and morphology-based diseases on the pooled dataset with ResNet: As the training set size decreases, the individual label AUCs (i.e., individual disease-level AUCs) follow a similar trend to the dataset-level AUCs described above. However, the extent of AUC decline varies across different groups of diseases. For example, when the training set is reduced from 5% to 1%, the AUCs for rhythm-based diseases drop by 0.10 to 0.24. In contrast, morphology-based diseases exhibit greater variability, with AUC declines ranging from 0.05 to 0.33. This contrast indicates morphology-based classification requires more training samples for stable learning, likely due to greater complexity in feature patterns compared to rhythm-based diagnoses.

Comparison between two test sets with ResNet: The observations about the pooled test set described above also occur on the CSN test set. However, when using 5% or less of the training data, the decline in Micro-AUC is more

Fig. 3: The test results per training set size using ResNet. The size is represented as a relative proportion of the full training set. The blue color represents the pooled test set, while the orange color represents the CSN test set. The shaded regions around the lines represent standard deviation.

pronounced on the CSN test set compared to the pooled test set. This suggests that models trained on limited data exhibit reduced generalizability, particularly when faced with distribution shifts in the test data. Besides, Micro-AUC exhibits greater sensitivity to extreme data reduction (1% training data), particularly on the CSN test set, revealing limitations in model generalizability under severe data constraints. The larger Micro-AUC declines suggest class-specific performance degradation that Macro-AUC may obscure.

Comparison between ResNet and Transformer models:

While both architectures follow similar degradation patterns, Transformer shows greater sensitivity to data reduction (0.33 vs 0.14 Macro-AUC drop at 1% data) and consistently poorer performance on morphology-based labels. ResNet’s superior data efficiency is particularly evident in low-data regimes, maintaining better absolute performance across all training set sizes.

In summary, the performance of ResNet and Transformer on both test sets degrades at both the dataset and disease level when the training set size is reduced. The magnitude of the decrease in AUC varies across disease groups and AI models. Halving the size of the training set can lead to statistically significant differences in the results, even if they are numerically small. ResNet demonstrates robust performance with 20% training data, with graceful degradation until 5% data. Below this threshold, rhythm-based predictions degrade more consistently than morphology-based ones, while Micro-AUC reveals important class-specific effects. The consistent cross-dataset patterns and Transformer comparisons suggest these findings reflect fundamental requirements for ECG analysis rather than model-specific behaviors. ResNet emerges as the more data-efficient architecture, particularly for morphology-based classification tasks.

B. Data Augmentation

Figures 4 and 5 summarize the test results of training the reference model (ResNet) when each augmentation strategy (i.e., transformation) was applied individually on the full training set and when all augmentation strategies were applied sequentially across varying training set sizes, respectively.

Changes in Macro-AUC on the pooled dataset with ResNet when varying the settings for data augmentation: When augmentation are applied individually, ResNet demonstrates stable Macro-AUC performance on the pooled test set, with differences remaining insignificant across all augmentation methods. This robustness persists when augmentation are applied sequentially, except at the extreme 1% training data size where sequential augmentations cause significant Macro-AUC degradation (up to 0.05 decrease). The model maintains consistent performance across both individual and combined augmentation scenarios, suggesting inherent resilience to signal augmentations in typical training conditions.

Comparison between Macro-AUC and Micro-AUC on the pooled dataset with ResNet: Individual augmentations yield minimal Macro-AUC changes ($\leq +0.01$) (but produce measurable Micro-AUC improvements (+0.017 \sim +0.023) on the CSN test set, particularly for RandomStretch and MultiplyTriangle methods). When applied sequentially, augmentations show similar trends - Micro-AUC benefits are more pronounced than Macro-AUC changes, with the largest divergence occurring at 20% training data size (Micro-AUC +0.015 vs Macro-AUC +0.003). This pattern holds across both individual and sequential augmentation approaches, confirming that instance-level gains often exceed class-averaged improvements.

Comparison between rhythm-based and morphology-based diseases on the pooled dataset with ResNet: For individual augmentations, rhythm-based labels show mixed responses (atrial flutter AUC +0.03 with noise augmentation but -0.02 with flipping), while morphology-based labels exhibit more consistent small gains (up to +0.04 for left bundle branch block). Sequential augmentations amplify these effects: rhythm-based small-class conditions (premature atrial contraction and sinus arrhythmia) gain up to +0.05 AUC, while morphology-based labels like right axis deviation show progressive benefits (+0.03 \sim +0.07) as training data decreases. Notably, 1st degree AV block consistently underperforms with any augmentation approach (individual or sequential).

Comparison between two test sets with ResNet: Individual augmentations produce greater Micro-AUC improvements on the CSN test set (+0.020 \sim +0.023) compared to the pooled set (less than +0.005), particularly for time-domain methods like RandomStretch. Sequential augmentations further accentuate this dataset divergence: CSN shows consistent improvements for rhythm-based labels (e.g., atrial flutter +0.04), while the pooled set exhibits slight decreases (-0.02) for the same conditions. morphology-based labels demonstrate similar cross-dataset variability, with left bundle branch block gaining +0.05 on CSN versus +0.03 on pooled when augmentations are combined.

Comparison between ResNet and Transformer models: When augmentations are applied individually, Transformer suffers significant performance drops (Macro-AUC -0.114 \sim -0.122) from basic operations like flipping, while ResNet remains stable. This gap widens with sequential augmentations: Transformers show severe degradation (up to -0.15 Macro-AUC) at $\geq 10\%$ training set sizes, whereas ResNet maintains performance except at 1% data. Both architectures display

Fig. 4: The test results per each data augmentation method using ResNet. The blue color represents the pooled test set, while the orange color represents the CSN test set.

Fig. 5: The test results per probability set for each fraction using ResNet. The blue color represents the pooled test set, while the orange color represents the CSN test set.

similar trends - morphology-based labels are more vulnerable than rhythm labels - but Transformer’s sensitivity is markedly greater across all augmentation approaches.

In summary, ResNet demonstrates superior stability across both individual and sequential augmentation strategies compared to Transformer, particularly for morphology-based diagnosis. Micro-AUC improvements are consistently more pronounced than Macro-AUC changes, especially on distribution-shifted (CSN) data. Sequential augmentations amplify benefits for rare conditions while maintaining performance on common ones, except at extremely low (1%) training data volumes. The consistent architectural differences highlight ResNet’s advantages for ECG analysis under diverse augmentation scenarios.

C. Data Filtering

Figure 6 summarizes the test results of training the reference model (ResNet) with different bandwidth settings. We can observe the following.

Changes in Macro-AUC on the pooled dataset with ResNet when varying the settings for data filtering: When applying the typically recommended bandwidth filters, ResNet’s Macro-AUC remains stable, with differences of at most 0.01 compared to unfiltered data. However, reducing the upper cut-off frequency to 1 Hz causes a significant drop in performance, decreasing Macro-AUC by 0.126.

Comparison between Macro-AUC and Micro-AUC on the pooled dataset with ResNet: Both metrics exhibit minimal changes (≤ 0.01 difference) with typical filtering settings. However, at 1 Hz, Macro-AUC declines more sharply

(0.126) than Micro-AUC (0.053). This divergence suggests that frequency restrictions disproportionately affect certain classes, particularly those reliant on higher-frequency signal components.

Comparison between rhythm-based and morphology-based diseases on the pooled dataset with ResNet: Rhythm-based classes benefit slightly (up to +0.05 AUC) with cut-offs ≥ 5 Hz, likely due to their dependence on higher-frequency features like P-waves and R-R intervals. In contrast, morphology-based classes respond inconsistently: some improve (e.g., 1st degree AV block), while others degrade (e.g., low QRS voltages). This implies that morphology-based classes rely on a broader frequency spectrum, with some classes sensitive to specific bandpass ranges.

Comparison between two test sets with ResNet: Performance trends differ across datasets. On the pooled set, ≥ 5 Hz cut-offs improve rhythm-based classes but harm select morphology-based labels (e.g., 0.1 for incomplete right bundle branch block). Conversely, on the CSN set, rhythm labels decline (up to 0.09), while morphology-based labels improve substantially (up to +0.19). These discrepancies may stem from differences in label prevalence, recording quality, or dataset-specific noise characteristics.

Comparison between ResNet and Transformer models: Both models exhibit nearly identical behavior: AUC differences are 0.02 across typical cut-offs, and both suffer comparable declines at 1 Hz (e.g., 0.126 vs. 0.127 Macro-AUC on the pooled set). Transformer shows marginally larger variability (up to 0.02 AUC difference vs. ResNet’s 0.01) when reducing cut-offs, but the overall trends align, suggesting architectural differences have minimal impact on frequency sensitivity.

In summary, ResNet’s performance is robust to typical filtering but degrades sharply with aggressive low-pass filtering (≤ 1 Hz), particularly for rhythm-based labels. Macro-AUC is more affected than Micro-AUC, highlighting class-specific sensitivity. Dataset and label-type disparities suggest that optimal filtering may require task-specific tuning. Transformer mirrors ResNet’s behavior, indicating generalizability of these findings across architectures.

D. Signal Length

Figure 7 summarizes the test results of training the reference model (ResNet) with different signal settings. We can observe the following.

Changes in Macro-AUC on the pooled dataset with ResNet when varying the settings for signal length: ResNet demonstrates strong resilience to reduced signal lengths, with only modest Macro-AUC decreases of 0.02 for 50% length and 0.10 for 10% length on the pooled test set. Performance degradation follows a gradual pattern proportional to signal reduction, suggesting the model can effectively utilize partial ECG segments while maintaining diagnostic capability.

Comparison between Macro-AUC and Micro-AUC on the pooled dataset with ResNet: Both metrics show similar sensitivity to signal truncation, with Micro-AUC exhibiting slightly greater declines (0.03 vs 0.02 for 50% length; 0.11 vs 0.10 for 10% length). This parallel behavior indicates

Fig. 6: The test results from the bandwidth experiments using ResNet. The blue color represents the pooled test set, while the orange color represents the CSN test set.

consistent performance impacts across both class-averaged and instance-level evaluation perspectives when analyzing short-ecg signals.

Comparison between rhythm-based and morphology-based diseases on the pooled dataset with ResNet: Rhythm-based labels show greater variability in response to signal truncation, with specific conditions like premature atrial contraction experiencing up to 0.14 Macro-AUC decline, while most morphology-based labels remain stable (≤ 0.04 Macro-AUC difference). The 10% length reduction particularly impacts rhythm interpretation, suggesting these diagnoses rely more on extended temporal patterns than morphological features.

Comparison between two test sets with ResNet: Performance trends remain consistent across test sets, with comparable AUC decreases for both Macro- (0.10 pooled vs 0.09 CSN) and Micro- (0.11 pooled vs 0.16 CSN) AUCs at 10% signal length. The slightly larger Micro-AUC decline on CSN data may indicate greater sensitivity to signal truncation in certain distribution-shifted cases.

Comparison between ResNet and Transformer models: ResNet shows superior robustness to signal truncation compared to Transformer, particularly for morphology-based labels. While Transformer maintains rhythm-based label performance across lengths, its AUCs for morphology-based labels drop significantly, contrasting with ResNet’s more balanced preservation of both diagnostic capabilities. Both architectures exhibit similar Macro-AUC declines (0.09 \sim 0.12) at extreme truncation (10% length).

In summary, ResNet maintains reliable performance with signal truncation, showing graceful degradation proportional to length reduction. Its balanced preservation of both rhythm and morphology detection contrasts with Transformer’s specialized

Fig. 7: The test results per each reduced length using ResNet. The blue color represents the pooled test set, while the orange color represents the CSN test set.

but uneven capabilities. The consistent cross-dataset patterns suggest these findings reflect fundamental ECG analysis requirements, with ResNet demonstrating particular advantages for working with partial ECG recordings.

E. Label Correlations

(Figure 8 summarizes the test results of training the reference model (ResNet) with different classification type multilabel vs. binary). We can observe the following.

Changes in Macro-AUC on the pooled dataset with ResNet when varying the settings for label correlations: ResNet demonstrates consistent performance advantages in multilabel classification compared to binary classification across most training set sizes, with Macro-AUC differences typically ranging between 0.05 \sim 0.06 for 20%, 10%, and 5% training data. The performance gap narrows to ≤ 0.02 for other configurations, indicating multilabel learning’s superior capability in capturing comprehensive ECG patterns. Only at the extreme 1% training data size does binary classification show comparable performance.

Comparison between Macro-AUC and Micro-AUC on the pooled dataset with ResNet: Both evaluation metrics follow similar trends, with multilabel models consistently outperforming binary approaches. The Micro-AUC differences mirror Macro-AUC patterns, maintaining stable gaps of 0.05 \sim 0.06 for mid-range training sizes (20% \sim 5%) and shrinking to ≤ 0.02 in other cases. This parallel behavior suggests consistent advantages of multilabel learning across both class-averaged and instance-level evaluation perspectives.

Comparison between rhythm-based and morphology-based diseases on the pooled dataset with ResNet: Rhythm-based labels show pronounced performance gaps between multilabel and binary approaches (0.15 \sim 0.25 Macro-AUC decrease for atrial flutter, sinus arrhythmia, and premature atrial contraction), while morphology-based labels exhibit more variable but generally smaller differences (typically ≤ 0.13). The exception is T wave inversion, showing consistent 0.05 \sim 0.13 Macro-AUC advantages for multilabel learning across all training sizes.

Comparison between two test sets with ResNet: Performance trends remain consistent across test sets, with rhythm-based labels showing similar magnitude of multilabel advantages (0.15 \sim 0.25 Macro-AUC differences). Morphology-

Fig. 8: The test results when comparing binary classification to multilabel classification per training data size using ResNet. The blue color represents the pooled test set, while the orange color represents the CSN test set. The shaded regions around the lines represent SD.

based labels demonstrate some dataset-specific variations, particularly for left bundle branch block on the CSN test set (0.12 Macro-AUC difference at 5% training size), suggesting certain morphological features may benefit more from multilabel learning in specific data distributions.

Comparison between ResNet and Transformer models:

Transformer shows more extreme sensitivity to classification strategy, with morphology-based labels suffering dramatic performance drops (up to 0.42 Macro-AUC difference) in binary classification. While rhythm-based labels maintain relatively stable performance (≤ 0.02 differences), the architecture’s struggle with binary morphology-based classification highlights ResNet’s more robust handling of both learning paradigms, particularly for structural abnormalities.

In summary, multilabel classification consistently outperforms binary classification for ECG analysis, with ResNet demonstrating more stable advantages (typically $0.05 \sim 0.06$ Macro-AUC) compared to Transformer’s extreme variability. Rhythm diagnoses benefit substantially from multilabel learning, while morphology diagnoses show more condition-specific improvements. The consistent cross-dataset patterns and architectural comparisons suggest multilabel training better captures the interdependent nature of cardiac abnormalities, with ResNet proving particularly effective in this paradigm.

F. Summarization

Table II shows the key findings of impact between ECG-related factors and Deep classifiers. The analysis in this study reveals a fundamental impact between ECG-related factors and deep learning model performance, demonstrating that domain-specific considerations are more critical than generic model architecture improvements. Across all tested scenarios - including variations in training set size, signal quality (data filtering and signal length), augmentation strategies, and label correlations - ECG characteristics consistently emerge as the primary drivers of model performance. For instance, the data shows that even simple filtering choices like low-pass cutoff frequencies (≤ 1 Hz causing 0.126 Macro-AUC drops) or training set reductions (5% data threshold for stable performance) create larger impacts than switching between

ResNet and Transformer architectures (≤ 0.03 Macro-AUC difference). These findings prove that ECG analysis has intrinsic requirements that must guide model development, particularly regarding temporal resolution needs for rhythm analysis versus morphological feature preservation for morphological abnormalities.

The consistent patterns across multiple experimental dimensions provide compelling evidence for this ECG-model synergy. First, the differential sensitivity of rhythm versus morphological diagnoses to factors like signal length (rhythm AUC drops up to 0.14 vs morphology ≤ 0.04) and data augmentation reveals how cardiac electrical patterns demand specific architectural handling. Second, the superior performance of multilabel classification ($0.05 \sim 0.25$ AUC gains over binary) across all test conditions demonstrates that modeling physiological interdependencies between cardiac conditions is more important than model selection. Third, the dataset-specific effects - particularly the greater benefits of augmentation on distribution-shifted CSN data - show that real-world clinical variability must be addressed at the data level before model optimization.

These results collectively prove that effective ECG analysis requires specialized solutions rather than generic deep learning approaches. ResNet’s consistent superiority over Transformer across all tested scenarios stems from its innate compatibility with ECG characteristics - particularly its local feature extraction for morphological patterns and temporal invariance for rhythm analysis. The findings suggest that future ECG AI development should prioritize: (1) ECG-related preprocessing that preserves diagnostically critical frequencies and segments, (2) learning paradigms that capture cardiac condition interdependencies, and (3) architectures optimized for the distinct feature types needed for rhythm versus morphology analysis. This demonstrated synergy between ECG domain knowledge and model design principles provides a clear roadmap for developing more effective cardiac diagnostic AI.

G. Discussion

The findings of this study highlight that ECG-related data factors exert a stronger influence on classification performance than architectural differences between commonly used deep models. Although some outcomes, such as the benefits of longer signals, the detrimental effects of noise, and the advantages of multilabel classification, may align with prior expectations, what has been lacking in the literature is a systematic and quantitative verification of these phenomena across diverse datasets, label types, and model families. By rigorously establishing the extent to which each factor alters performance, this work provides a consolidated empirical foundation upon which future research can reliably build.

A key insight from our analysis is the differing sensitivity of rhythm- and morphology-based classifications to data conditions. Morphological features demand larger training datasets, likely due to greater inter-patient variability and subtler waveform deviations, whereas rhythm features are more affected by reductions in signal length. These trends underscore the need to tailor data collection and preprocessing strategies to the

TABLE II: Key Findings of Impact Between ECG-Related Factors and Deep Classifiers

Factors	Experimental Observation	Impact Insight
Deep Models	ResNet and Transformer demonstrate ≤ 0.03 difference in both Macro- and Micro-AUCs across test sets	Architectural differences between Deep models have minimal impact on overall ECG classification accuracy.
Data Size	ResNet outperforms Transformer at all data sizes. With 1% data, Macro-AUC drops 0.14 (ResNet) vs. 0.33 (Transformer). Micro-AUC is more affected under distribution shift. morphology-based labels degrade more rapidly.	Model performance depends heavily on sufficient training size. ResNet is more data-efficient. Data scarcity amplifies label-specific and architecture-specific weaknesses, highlighting the need for synergy-aware model design under low-resource conditions.
Data Augmentation	ResNet shows stable performance across individual and sequential augmentations. Transformer suffers significant degradation (up to -0.15 Macro-AUC). Micro-AUC gains (+0.015 ~ +0.023) are more evident than Macro-AUC. CSN set shows more benefit.	Augmentations benefit Micro-AUC and rare classes, especially under distribution shift. ResNet demonstrates superior augmentation robustness. Synergy is evident: augmentation effectiveness depends on architecture and label characteristics.
Signal Length	ResNet degrades gracefully with shorter signals (Macro-AUC -0.10 at 10% length). Rhythm-based labels show more decline than morphology-based. Transformer loses more morphology accuracy.	Shorter signals affect rhythm-based labels more, due to reliance on temporal patterns. ResNet’s robustness shows better synergy with ECG signal variability. Transformer struggles with general pattern loss.
Data Filtering	ResNet and Transformer are stable under typical filters. Severe low-pass (1 Hz) causes -0.13 Macro-AUC drop. Rhythm-based classes more affected. CSN test shows divergent responses (e.g., +0.19 gain for some morphology labels).	Performance is sensitive to signal preprocessing. Label-type and dataset-specific filtering effects reveal the importance of synergistic tuning between model and ECG preprocessing pipeline.
Label Correlations	Multilabel classification consistently outperforms binary classification in ECG analysis. ResNet shows stable Macro-AUC gains (typically 0.05 ~ 0.06) across most training sizes (5% ~ 20%), particularly for rhythm-based conditions like atrial flutter and sinus arrhythmia (up to 0.25 Macro-AUC improvement). Binary classification only matches performance at extreme low-data settings (1%).	ResNet exhibits robust advantages in capturing label dependencies, especially for rhythm-based arrhythmias. Transformer suffers in binary classification, with Macro-AUC drops up to 0.42 for morphology-based conditions, highlighting its sensitivity. Multilabel training enables both models to leverage inter-label patterns, with ResNet offering more consistent gains across datasets and label types.

diagnostic target and demonstrate the importance of validating intuitive expectations with controlled evidence for clinical AI deployment.

Another important observation is that performance trends, rather than absolute thresholds, provide actionable guidance. It is neither practical nor meaningful to define a universal “sufficient signal length” or “noise tolerance.” Instead, the consistent degradation patterns reported here illustrate how performance varies with incremental changes in data conditions. These trends allow practitioners to anticipate model vulnerabilities in different contexts, such as low-resource training scenarios or distribution shifts, and to prioritize improvements in data quality and sufficiency accordingly.

Our objective was not to benchmark every emerging architecture, including the latest state-of-the-art models, but to assess ECG-related data factors using representative families of methods. The observed effects are primarily driven by input signal properties and dataset characteristics rather than architectural innovations. While including additional models could broaden the comparative scope, the central findings are expected to remain valid and generalizable across architectures.

This work remains primarily empirical and does not yet provide a formal theoretical model of the observed synergies between ECG data characteristics and classifier performance. Nevertheless, by systematically quantifying these effects, it establishes a robust empirical foundation for future mechanistic studies and offers practical guidance for data collection, preprocessing, and model training in real-world ECG applications.

Finally, the study emphasizes the value of analyzing data factors in isolation before attempting more complex interaction modeling. Although multi-factorial dependencies undoubtedly exist, isolating individual variables provides interpretable baselines and reveals which dimensions exert the greatest influence. These baselines represent an essential starting point for future

factorial or mechanistic analyses, enabling the community to move beyond anecdotal observations toward reproducible, evidence-driven understanding.

H. Limitation

While the overall averaged performance metrics indicate robustness in our findings, they do not provide a complete picture of the models’ performance on rarer CVDs that were not included in the dataset. Another limitation is that, although the study dataset includes ECG recordings from five different sources, over 70% of the recordings are from Chinese populations, which may restrict the generalizability of our results to patient groups in other countries. Additionally, the parameter settings for ResNet were kept fixed across all experiments, which may limit the ability to assess the model’s performance under different configurations. Finally, we only used the AUC as the evaluation metric, which limits the scope of performance analysis across other important metrics.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we conducted a comprehensive investigation into the interplay between typical ECG-related factors and deep learning classifiers. Specifically, we examined five critical factors, training set size, data augmentation, data filtering, signal length, and label correlations across two representative deep models (ResNet and Transformer) and four public real-world ECG datasets.

Our analysis reveals that the performance of deep classifiers varies significantly depending on how these ECG-related factors are configured. Notably, the same model can perform substantially better or worse under different settings, occasionally even outperforming more complex architectures. ResNet, in particular, often outperforms Transformer not due to superior architectural sophistication, but due to its robustness under adverse data conditions such as low signal quality or limited training samples.

Furthermore, we find that the influence of data-centric factors, including training size, augmentation, signal length, and filtering, can exceed the impact of model architecture, especially in realistic clinical settings where data scarcity and distribution shifts are common.

These findings underscore the critical importance of considering the synergy between ECG data characteristics and model design. Rather than focusing exclusively on architectural innovations, future ECG-based AI research should prioritize data-centric optimization strategies to fully unlock the potential of deep learning in clinical applications.

CODE AVAILABILITY

The source code that was used to perform the experiments can be found at <https://github.com/UTU-Health-Research/dl-ecg-classifier>. It contains functionalities to 1) save demographic information, diagnostic labels and ECG paths to a CSV file which is used during model training and evaluation, 2) store parameters and other training and validation settings for each run as YAML files, 3) map the AHA codes to the SNOMED CT codes and vice versa, 4) preprocess ECGs using different augmentations, 5) and train and run models.

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Supplementary material for the paper: Impact of ECG Characteristics on Deep Classifiers

Tuija Leinonen, Jiawei Yang, David Wong, Antti Airola and Matti Kaisti

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Table S1: Label distributions per set in our study, sorted by their total frequency. In total, the training set contained 41,715 ECGs pooled from the four datasets, including 4,279 ECGs from the CPSC and CPSC-Extra dataset, 6,225 ECGs from the G12EC dataset, 14,921 ECGs from the PTB and PTB-XL dataset, and 16,290 ECGs from the SPH dataset. The pooled test set contained the remaining 17,909 ECGs from these datasets, and the CSN test set included 43,814 ECGs. The colored rows are the rhythm-based labels, which is used to clarify the ECG analysis.

Dx	SNOMEDCTCode	Training set	Pooled test set	CSN test set	Total
Sinus rhythm	426783006	26303	11275	8125	45703
Sinus bradycardia	426177001	3549	1521	16559	21629
T wave abnormal	164934002	4699	2016	7043	13758
Sinus tachycardia	427084000	2181	935	7255	10371
Atrial flutter	164890007	289	124	8060	8473
Left axis deviation	39732003	4357	1867	1545	7769
Atrial fibrillation	164889003	2903	1245	1780	5928
Sinus arrhythmia	427393009	1953	838	2550	5341
T wave inversion	59931005	901	386	2877	4164
1st degree AV block	270492004	1993	854	1192	4039
Right bundle branch block	59118001	2177	933	649	3759
Premature atrial contraction	284470004	1585	680	1312	3577
Incomplete right bundle branch block	713426002	2009	861	246	3116
Left anterior fascicular block	445118002	1372	588	380	2340
Low QRS voltages	251146004	614	264	1043	1921
Right axis deviation	47665007	412	176	853	1441
Left bundle branch block	164909002	788	337	240	1365

Table S2: Handcrafted features that were used for both Transformer and the benchmark models, as in [45]. Here, μ and σ represent mean and standard deviation, Δ RR refers to the difference in RR intervals, and SWT stands for stationary wavelet transform.

Rank	Feature	Rank	Feature
1	HR_{min}	11	pNN60
2	T wave multiscale permutation entropy σ	12	SWT composition level 4 entropy
3	HR_{max}	13	RR interval intra-cluster distance, cluster 2
4	T wave multiscale permutation entropy median	14	Heart rate activity
5	RMSSD	15	Δ RR $_{min}$
6	P wave correlation coefficient	16	T wave permutation entropy σ
7	RR interval median	17	P wave sample entropy σ
8	Heart rate μ	18	SWT decomposition level 3 entropy
9	RR interval intra-cluster distance, cluster 3	19	Median P wave approximate entropy
10	RR interval Fisher information	20	R peak approximate entropy

1 Test results of Transformer for the Result section

Figure S1: Experiment results for data size factor

Figure S2: Experiment results for label correlations

Figure S3: Experiment results for data filtering

Figure S4: Experiment results for signal length

Figure S5: Experiment results for label correlations by applying data augmentation methods individually

Figure S6: Experiment results for label correlations by applying data augmentation methods Sequentially

2 AUC tables for the Result section

Table S3: The preliminary results for the data augmentation experiments, based on which the two probability sets of $\{p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.5\}$ and $\{p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.2\}$ were selected for the final experiments. The bold rows correspond to the fraction results without augmentation applied, and therefore, the 100 % row refers to the reference model. The model used was ResNet, and the difference Δ computed is the difference between the experimental model and the reference ResNet model.

	Pooled test set						CSN test set					
	Macro-AUC			Micro-AUC			Macro-AUC			Micro-AUC		
	Mean	SD	Δ_{exp}	Mean	SD	Δ_{exp}	Mean	SD	Δ_{exp}	Mean	SD	Δ_{exp}
100 %	0.966			0.983			0.941			0.930		
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.2$	0.966		-0.000	0.985		0.001	0.948		0.007	0.942		0.013
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.5$	0.962		-0.005	0.982		-0.001	0.944		0.004	0.943		0.013
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.8$	0.960		-0.006	0.981		-0.002	0.940		-0.001	0.929		-0.001
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.2$	0.961		-0.005	0.982		-0.001	0.947		0.006	0.944		0.015
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.5$	0.952		-0.014	0.977		-0.007	0.937		-0.004	0.937		0.007
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.8$	0.940		-0.027	0.971		-0.013	0.933		-0.008	0.917		-0.013
10 %	0.918	0.006	-0.048	0.961	0.004	-0.023	0.893	0.009	-0.047	0.900	0.022	-0.030
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.2$	0.923	0.004	-0.007	0.963	0.003	0.033	0.905	0.001	-0.025	0.910	0.008	-0.020
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.5$	0.922	0.007	-0.007	0.964	0.003	0.034	0.908	0.008	-0.021	0.901	0.013	-0.029
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.8$	0.922	0.002	-0.007	0.965	0.000	0.036	0.909	0.001	-0.021	0.911	0.009	-0.019
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.2$	0.924	0.003	-0.006	0.965	0.002	0.035	0.908	0.002	-0.022	0.916	0.001	-0.014
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.5$	0.917	0.000	-0.012	0.961	0.001	0.031	0.907	0.002	-0.023	0.916	0.009	-0.014
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.8$	0.863	0.015	-0.067	0.939	0.007	0.009	0.852	0.015	-0.077	0.861	0.021	-0.069
5 %	0.880	0.008	-0.086	0.941	0.005	-0.042	0.848	0.006	-0.093	0.851	0.016	-0.078
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.2$	0.883	0.002	-0.047	0.943	0.001	0.013	0.847	0.004	-0.083	0.832	0.013	-0.098
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.5$	0.895	0.014	-0.035	0.950	0.004	0.020	0.866	0.016	-0.064	0.849	0.024	-0.081
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.8$	0.887	0.008	-0.042	0.948	0.002	0.018	0.864	0.009	-0.066	0.867	0.019	-0.063
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.2$	0.885	0.008	-0.045	0.944	0.003	0.014	0.857	0.007	-0.072	0.848	0.011	-0.082
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.5$	0.870	0.010	-0.059	0.940	0.006	0.010	0.855	0.014	-0.075	0.840	0.020	-0.090
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.8$	0.742	0.009	-0.188	0.883	0.004	-0.047	0.748	0.007	-0.182	0.730	0.009	-0.200
1 %	0.743	0.012	-0.224	0.859	0.003	-0.124	0.718	0.013	-0.222	0.728	0.028	-0.202
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.2$	0.741	0.014	-0.188	0.860	0.008	-0.069	0.713	0.016	-0.217	0.731	0.022	-0.199
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.5$	0.724	0.065	-0.206	0.854	0.035	-0.076	0.699	0.066	-0.231	0.700	0.086	-0.230
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.8$	0.656	0.014	-0.274	0.832	0.007	-0.098	0.645	0.008	-0.285	0.652	0.003	-0.278
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.2$	0.732	0.007	-0.198	0.857	0.009	-0.073	0.713	0.014	-0.217	0.740	0.040	-0.190
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.5$	0.666	0.011	-0.264	0.842	0.011	-0.088	0.670	0.007	-0.260	0.680	0.011	-0.250
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.8$	0.677	0.014	-0.252	0.859	0.006	-0.071	0.681	0.015	-0.249	0.682	0.007	-0.248

Table S4: The test results from the bandwidth experiments, where the ECG data is resampled at 500 Hz. The difference Δ computed is the difference between the experimental model and the reference ResNet model.

	Pooled test set				CSN test set			
	ResNet		Transformer		ResNet		Transformer	
	Macro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Micro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Macro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Micro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Macro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Micro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Macro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Micro-AUC (Δ_{exp})
Reference	0.965	0.982	0.944	0.975	0.938	0.928	0.924	0.935
Metadata	0.652	0.847	0.649	0.843	0.664	0.676	0.662	0.66
Low-pass								
150	0.964 (-0.0002)	0.984 (0.0013)	0.943 (-0.0214)	0.974 (-0.0080)	0.944 (0.0058)	0.942 (0.0137)	0.921 (-0.0167)	0.933 (0.0044)
Bandpass								
[0.67, 40]	0.965 (0.0006)	0.984 (0.0019)	0.940 (-0.0247)	0.972 (-0.0103)	0.944 (0.0060)	0.930 (0.0016)	0.918 (-0.0201)	0.922 (-0.0065)
[0.67, 20]	0.963 (-0.0015)	0.983 (0.0003)	0.940 (-0.0248)	0.974 (-0.0086)	0.934 (-0.0035)	0.933 (0.0041)	0.917 (-0.0210)	0.913 (-0.0152)
[0.67, 10]	0.962 (-0.0025)	0.983 (0.0003)	0.939 (-0.0255)	0.972 (-0.0101)	0.945 (0.0075)	0.943 (0.0143)	0.914 (-0.0241)	0.920 (-0.0085)
[0.67, 5]	0.956 (-0.0085)	0.980 (-0.0024)	0.935 (-0.0297)	0.971 (-0.0117)	0.940 (0.0025)	0.935 (0.0067)	0.911 (-0.0266)	0.922 (-0.0069)
[0.67, 1]	0.839 (-0.1260)	0.929 (-0.0528)	0.816 (-0.1485)	0.925 (-0.0574)	0.806 (-0.1316)	0.837 (-0.0913)	0.798 (-0.1398)	0.846 (-0.0829)

Table S5: The final test results from the training data size, data augmentation and classification type experiments. The difference Δ computed is the difference between the experimental model and the reference ResNet model. The bold row presents the results of the training data size experiments without applying data augmentation. For each sample size, ten pools were randomly selected from the training set, except for the 50 % fraction for which two pools were used. The total numbers of ECGs n for each fraction are $n \approx 420$ for 1 %, $n \approx 2,077$ for 5 %, $n \approx 4,170$ for 10 %, $n \approx 8,358$ for 20 %, and $n \approx 20,882$ for 50 %. The probabilities p_1 and p_2 refer to the probability that an individual augmentation method is applied, and the probability that the augmentations are applied in general, respectively.

	Pooled test set												CSN test set											
	ResNet			Transformer			ResNet			Transformer			ResNet			Transformer								
	Mean	SD	Δ_{exp}	Mean	SD	Δ_{exp}	Mean	SD	Δ_{exp}	Mean	SD	Δ_{exp}	Mean	SD	Δ_{exp}	Mean	SD	Δ_{exp}	Mean	SD	Δ_{exp}			
100 %	0.966			0.983			0.937			0.972			0.941			0.930			0.912			0.918		
Binary	0.957		-0.009	0.981		-0.002	0.816		-0.151	0.924		-0.059	0.932		-0.009	0.925		-0.005	0.797		-0.144	0.840		-0.090
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.5$	0.962		-0.005	0.982		-0.001	0.818		-0.149	0.925		-0.058	0.944		0.004	0.943		0.013	0.800		-0.141	0.846		-0.083
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.2$	0.961		-0.005	0.982		-0.001	0.816		-0.150	0.925		-0.059	0.947		0.006	0.944		0.015	0.798		-0.143	0.843		-0.086
50 %	0.959	0.004	-0.007	0.981	0.003	-0.002	0.931	0.001	-0.035	0.970	0.000	-0.014	0.940	0.004	-0.001	0.937	0.007	0.007	0.911	0.001	-0.030	0.923	0.002	-0.007
Binary	0.944	0.000	-0.023	0.974	0.001	-0.010	0.807	0.000	-0.160	0.922	0.000	-0.062	0.916	0.003	-0.024	0.896	0.003	-0.033	0.789	0.003	-0.151	0.841	0.001	-0.089
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.5$	0.959	0.000	-0.007	0.981	0.000	-0.002	0.808	0.000	-0.158	0.923	0.000	-0.061	0.938	0.004	-0.003	0.936	0.006	0.006	0.790	0.002	-0.150	0.839	0.004	-0.091
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.2$	0.958	0.000	-0.009	0.981	0.000	-0.003	0.808	0.000	-0.159	0.922	0.000	-0.061	0.938	0.001	-0.002	0.944	0.002	0.014	0.790	0.001	-0.151	0.838	0.003	-0.091
20 %	0.944	0.001	-0.022	0.974	0.001	-0.010	0.901	0.008	-0.065	0.957	0.004	-0.026	0.920	0.004	-0.020	0.913	0.009	-0.017	0.880	0.008	-0.061	0.891	0.017	-0.039
Binary	0.898	0.010	-0.068	0.957	0.003	-0.027	0.790	0.002	-0.176	0.917	0.001	-0.067	0.870	0.009	-0.071	0.880	0.012	-0.050	0.776	0.003	-0.165	0.830	0.009	-0.100
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.5$	0.944	0.002	-0.022	0.974	0.001	-0.009	0.791	0.003	-0.176	0.918	0.000	-0.066	0.929	0.004	-0.011	0.925	0.011	-0.005	0.774	0.003	-0.166	0.828	0.005	-0.102
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.2$	0.942	0.003	-0.024	0.973	0.001	-0.011	0.791	0.003	-0.175	0.918	0.000	-0.066	0.927	0.005	-0.014	0.929	0.010	-0.001	0.775	0.004	-0.166	0.829	0.005	-0.101
10 %	0.918	0.006	-0.048	0.961	0.004	-0.023	0.868	0.030	-0.098	0.944	0.011	-0.040	0.893	0.009	-0.047	0.900	0.022	-0.030	0.846	0.025	-0.095	0.866	0.016	-0.064
Binary	0.860	0.008	-0.106	0.939	0.005	-0.045	0.765	0.002	-0.201	0.908	0.001	-0.075	0.835	0.009	-0.106	0.851	0.012	-0.079	0.755	0.004	-0.186	0.810	0.010	-0.119
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.5$	0.925	0.005	-0.041	0.964	0.002	-0.019	0.771	0.014	-0.196	0.909	0.005	-0.075	0.909	0.005	-0.031	0.909	0.016	-0.021	0.750	0.020	-0.191	0.812	0.014	-0.118
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.2$	0.921	0.006	-0.045	0.963	0.003	-0.020	0.767	0.002	-0.199	0.908	0.001	-0.076	0.905	0.008	-0.036	0.908	0.012	-0.022	0.750	0.004	-0.191	0.811	0.007	-0.119
5 %	0.880	0.008	-0.086	0.941	0.005	-0.042	0.834	0.010	-0.133	0.925	0.005	-0.059	0.848	0.006	-0.093	0.851	0.016	-0.078	0.797	0.017	-0.144	0.821	0.030	-0.109
Binary	0.822	0.013	-0.145	0.920	0.006	-0.063	0.725	0.004	-0.241	0.887	0.002	-0.097	0.791	0.013	-0.150	0.813	0.008	-0.117	0.712	0.012	-0.229	0.765	0.011	-0.165
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.5$	0.890	0.011	-0.076	0.947	0.005	-0.037	0.831	0.011	-0.135	0.927	0.004	-0.057	0.866	0.013	-0.075	0.863	0.022	-0.067	0.804	0.016	-0.137	0.835	0.021	-0.095
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.2$	0.879	0.010	-0.087	0.943	0.005	-0.041	0.831	0.009	-0.136	0.928	0.003	-0.055	0.858	0.014	-0.083	0.865	0.016	-0.065	0.798	0.016	-0.143	0.828	0.026	-0.102
1 %	0.743	0.012	-0.224	0.859	0.003	-0.124	0.599	0.010	-0.367	0.781	0.005	-0.202	0.718	0.013	-0.222	0.728	0.028	-0.202	0.587	0.011	-0.354	0.623	0.009	-0.307
Binary	0.731	0.014	-0.235	0.849	0.008	-0.134	0.652	0.015	-0.314	0.811	0.014	-0.173	0.703	0.016	-0.238	0.731	0.027	-0.199	0.647	0.016	-0.294	0.647	0.033	-0.282
$p_1 = 0.1, p_2 = 0.5$	0.703	0.040	-0.264	0.844	0.021	-0.140	0.597	0.008	-0.369	0.786	0.006	-0.197	0.685	0.038	-0.255	0.690	0.057	-0.239	0.583	0.011	-0.358	0.621	0.014	-0.308
$p_1 = 0.5, p_2 = 0.2$	0.697	0.053	-0.270	0.841	0.031	-0.142	0.598	0.010	-0.369	0.785	0.008	-0.199	0.682	0.048	-0.259	0.677	0.064	-0.253	0.582	0.012	-0.358	0.617	0.016	-0.312

Table S6: The test results from the experiments including standardization, individually and sequentially tested augmentation methods and signal length reductions. All models were trained on the full training set. The difference Δ computed is the difference between the experimental model and the reference ResNet model.

	Pooled test set				CSN test set			
	ResNet		Transformer		ResNet		Transformer	
	Macro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Micro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Macro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Micro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Macro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Micro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Macro-AUC (Δ_{exp})	Micro-AUC (Δ_{exp})
Reference	0.966	0.983	0.937	0.972	0.941	0.93	0.912	0.918
Metadata	0.652	0.847	0.649	0.843	0.664	0.676	0.662	0.66
Standardization								
	0.972 (0.0053)	0.986 (0.0026)	0.954 (-0.0129)	0.979 (-0.0044)	0.935 (-0.0056)	0.938 (0.0086)	0.919 (-0.0220)	0.933 (0.0037)
Augmentations								
Flip X	0.963 (-0.0035)	0.983 (-0.0006)	0.816 (-0.1506)	0.925 (-0.0586)	0.937 (-0.0041)	0.940 (0.0100)	0.798 (-0.1427)	0.845 (-0.0852)
Flip Y	0.960 (-0.0067)	0.982 (-0.0017)	0.816 (-0.1505)	0.925 (-0.0587)	0.938 (-0.0027)	0.943 (0.0136)	0.798 (-0.1429)	0.844 (-0.0863)
Multiply linear	0.967 (0.0005)	0.985 (0.0017)	0.940 (-0.0260)	0.973 (-0.0108)	0.941 (0.0004)	0.934 (0.0043)	0.916 (-0.0243)	0.930 (0.0005)
Multiply sine	0.964 (-0.0027)	0.983 (-0.0002)	0.939 (-0.0270)	0.972 (-0.0110)	0.942 (0.0018)	0.947 (0.0169)	0.917 (-0.0233)	0.934 (0.0044)
Multiply triangle	0.966 (-0.0000)	0.984 (0.0009)	0.941 (-0.0254)	0.973 (-0.0108)	0.949 (0.0088)	0.953 (0.0231)	0.919 (-0.0213)	0.935 (0.0050)
Noise	0.965 (-0.0014)	0.984 (0.0004)	0.939 (-0.0273)	0.972 (-0.0118)	0.947 (0.0059)	0.950 (0.0203)	0.917 (-0.0237)	0.932 (0.0017)
Notch filter	0.965 (-0.0011)	0.985 (0.0013)	0.942 (-0.0246)	0.974 (-0.0099)	0.943 (0.0024)	0.935 (0.0049)	0.920 (-0.0207)	0.932 (0.0020)
Random stretch	0.957 (-0.0090)	0.980 (-0.0031)	0.816 (-0.1507)	0.925 (-0.0586)	0.944 (0.0031)	0.953 (0.0228)	0.797 (-0.1432)	0.847 (-0.0829)
Resample linear	0.963 (-0.0029)	0.982 (-0.0012)	0.942 (-0.0245)	0.973 (-0.0105)	0.946 (0.0052)	0.943 (0.0137)	0.920 (-0.0203)	0.933 (0.0036)
Roll	0.965 (-0.0010)	0.984 (0.0007)	0.940 (-0.0260)	0.973 (-0.0103)	0.946 (0.0049)	0.939 (0.0093)	0.919 (-0.0221)	0.931 (0.0007)
Signal length								
50 %	0.945 (-0.0209)	0.950 (-0.0337)	0.816 (-0.1505)	0.925 (-0.0586)	0.922 (-0.0185)	0.903 (-0.0272)	0.798 (-0.1427)	0.846 (-0.0841)
10 %	0.864 (-0.1019)	0.878 (-0.1053)	0.816 (-0.1501)	0.925 (-0.0585)	0.854 (-0.0864)	0.772 (-0.1575)	0.798 (-0.1422)	0.846 (-0.0836)

3 Individual label AUCs

Figure S7: The individual AUCs in the model comparison. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S8: The individual AUCs in the model comparison. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S9: **Pooled test set.** The individual AUCs of the augmentation methods for Transformer that underperformed in the augmentation experiments. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S10: **CSN test set**. The individual AUCs of the augmentation methods for Transformer that underperformed in the augmentation experiments. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S11: **Pooled test set**. The test AUCs for each morphology-based diagnosis in the bandpass experiments. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S12: **CSN test set**. The test AUCs for each morphology-based diagnosis in the bandpass experiments. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S13: **Pooled test set**. The test AUCs for each rhythm-based diagnosis with and without data augmentations per each training data size. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S14: **CSN test set**. The test AUCs for each rhythm-based diagnosis with and without data augmentations per each training data size. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S15: **Pooled test set**. The test AUCs for each rhythm-based diagnosis with and without data augmentations per each training data size. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S16: **CSN test set**. The test AUCs for each rhythm-based diagnosis with and without data augmentations per each training data size. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S17: **Pooled test set**. The test AUCs for each morphology-based diagnosis with and without data augmentations per each training data size. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S18: **CSN test set**. The test AUCs for each morphology-based diagnosis with and without data augmentations per each training data size. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S19: The test AUCs for each rhythm-based diagnosis with each signal length. The blue color refers to the pooled test set, and the orange color refers to the CSN test set. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S20: The test AUCs for each morphology-based diagnosis with each signal length. The blue color refers to the pooled test set, and the orange color refers to the CSN test set. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S21: The test AUCs per each rhythm-based diagnosis in the classification type experiments using ResNet. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S22: The test AUCs per each rhythm-based diagnosis in the classification type experiments using Transformer. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S23: The test AUCs per each morphology-based diagnosis in the classification type experiments using ResNet. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.

Figure S24: The test AUCs per each morphology-based diagnosis in the classification type experiments using Transformer. The n mentioned for each CVD refers to the number of labels in the training set.